

How to Spin Up a Short-term Cloud Science Platform for Workshops

Alex Antunes
Johns Hopkins Applied Physics
Laboratory
Laurel, USA
0000-0002-3098-2602

Peter Shumate
Johns Hopkins Applied Physics
Laboratory
Laurel, USA
peter.shumate@jhuapl.edu

Shawn Polson
Laboratory for Atmospheric and
Space Physics
University of Colorado Boulder
Boulder, USA
shawn.polson@lasp.colorado.edu

Abstract— We discuss approaches for instantiating a short-term multi-user cloud for a large audience of cloud newcomers to teach better research software engineering skills within a domain-specific environment. We walk through our PyHC Summer School environment using the HelioCloud open source platform as the example, and discuss the logistics required and lessons learned.

Keywords— *gateways, cloud, research software engineer, containers, heliophysics*

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

We discuss gateway management approaches for transitory cloud environments including logistics, costs, guardrails, difficulties in syncing containers with outside tutorial contributors, risks, and benefits. We have spun up a week-long cloud environment to train early careers in the specific software and problems for heliophysics research, then torn it down afterwards. Each time we run this "PyHC Summer School", we improve our 'one button deploy' (spoiler: more than one button involved) and get better at container management to support the dozen sometimes conflicting science packages required by the environment. Success requires a mix of good technical basis and really structuring how both contributors and participants will interact with the system.

Our goal for running PyHC workshops is that engaging in research as a scientist or research software engineer requires domain knowledge, programming skills, and access to big datasets and enough compute power to grind through them. Building these skills gets boosted when experienced experts guide hands-on sessions within a uniform environment. Hence an open source cloud + container + data sources customized for the domain, with an easy interface such as Jupyter Notebooks, and sufficient cloud performance to scale.

However, running such an event efficiently involves crafting infrastructure, gathering tutorials from disparate community users, and creating a secure yet easily accessible environment that need only be ephemeral for the duration of the event. Unlike onboarding long-term users or creating tools for existing working groups, the logistics of spinning up a temporary yet fully functional scientific platform with domain-required software pre-loaded and tested are complex.

Specifically because such events are short-term and ephemeral, the risk profile is different than an institutional research environment. Concerns include the need for a pop-up architecture requiring minimal dev time to deploy, difficulties in creating a stable container that supports multiple presenter needs with potential package incompatibilities, and dealing with

costs and guardrails for the runtime. The design should minimize hurdles in attendees mastering the interface while limiting cost risk and exposure for the provider.

Our HelioCloud [1] platform is a Pangeo-derived open source set of cloud software for the heliophysics research community, available on github with details at heliocloud.org. Collaborating with the 'Python in Heliophysics Community' (PyHC.org, [2]) community, we've supported spinning up a Jupyter Daskhub AWS-backed framework for their week-long summer schools, where 400+ participants learn how to use both 'the cloud' and the scientific Python packages needed for research software engineering via hands-on problems presented by package developers that draw on real science problems. It is aimed at graduate students, early career scientists, and anyone eager to deepen their understanding of Python in the Heliophysics and Space Weather disciplines.

In our 90 minute tutorial, we walk through the basics needed to:

- (a) install a multiple user AWS cloud environment with easy sign on and Jupyter notebooks, backed by a single AWS account
- (b) resolve conflicting dependencies for the supporting container build (an iterative process, alas)
- (c) quickly onboard the participants with accounts pre-loaded with the content tutorials so everyone can try it from the user perspective
- (d) discuss the runtime support needed for the inevitable individual problems
- (e) discuss the cost risks we're willing to accept and the steps we took to mitigate these
- (f) provide statistics on usage, costs, and outcomes

We also invite questions and sharing of other solutions people have used.

- 1) Proposed length: 90 minutes
- 2) Recommend skill level:

Beginner to 'cloud', intermediate familiarity with containers and/or Python environments

- 3) Technology and/or Software requirements: Web connection required. We will have a pop-up environment set up with demo Notebooks (some including deliberate bugs) to provide an example runtime experience, and provide examples of the reporting cost dashboards the administrator will use.

REFERENCES

- [1] "HelioCloud: a community cloud-based approach to heliophysics analytics and software development. Thomas, B.A. et al, 2022, 2022AGUFM45B..01
- [2] Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC) Standards, 10.5281/zenodo.2529130